

Decomposition of Rural-Urban Inequality in the Usage of Mosquito Nets in Nigeria

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Abstract

Background of the study: According to the World Malaria Report, an estimated 249 million malaria cases occurred globally in 2022, with Nigeria accounting for over 1.3 million cases. Between 2009 and 2021, approximately 220 million insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) were distributed across 37 Nigerian states, resulting in increased usage among the general population and children under five. Despite these efforts, malaria incidence in Nigeria continues to show a cyclical pattern.

Objective of the study: This study examined the decomposition of factors contributing to rural-urban inequality in the use of mosquito nets in Nigeria.

Methodology: The study used the Blinder-Oaxaca Group Differences to decompose the determinants of rural-urban disparity in mosquito net utilisation. The data for this work were

extracted from the 2021 Nigeria Malaria Indicator Surveys (NMIS), which were piloted from 12 October to 4 December 2021. The study used data from the female file (15–49 years).

Results: Findings showed that educational gap, perception, north-south dichotomy, sex of the household head, disparity in wealth quintile in the rural-urban areas contributes positively and significantly to the inequality in the usage of mosquito net that exist in the rural-urban areas in Nigeria while a reduction in the age of the household head lower the inequality that exists in the usage of mosquito nets in the urban and rural areas.

Conclusion: The findings empirically establish that disparities in mosquito net usage across Nigeria's rural and urban areas are significantly exacerbated by a complex interplay of socioeconomic factors. Specifically, the observed inequality is positively driven by educational gaps, wealth quintile disparity, the north-south dichotomy, perception, and the sex of the household head. Conversely, reducing the age of the household head is confirmed to be an effective factor in mitigating this rural-urban inequality.

Unique Contribution: The research findings contribute to the understanding of the variables influencing ITN usage and provide insight into the factors that contribute to disparities in mosquito net usage in Nigeria's rural and urban areas.

Key recommendations: This study emphasises the importance of establishing achievable targets to alleviate disparities in education, socioeconomic status, and perceptions between rural and urban areas. By addressing these underlying inequalities, the government can effectively mitigate the rural-urban disparities in mosquito net usage.

Keywords: Mosquito net; rural-urban inequality; Blinder-Oaxaca; Malaria

Introduction

Malaria remains a serious public health concern in many nations, including Nigeria, and a major global health challenge, with an expected 247 million cases and 619,000 deaths from malaria in 2021 (Ibrahim et al., 2023). Despite over a century of study and global efforts to improve malaria prevention, diagnosis, and treatment, the disease still has a high burden of disease (Perera et al., 2022). Malaria-related deaths led to an economic loss of approximately US\$497 billion in sub-Saharan Africa, around 1.58% of the region's GDP. Approximately 60% of this loss (US\$286 billion) is attributed to climate-driven increases in malaria mortality (Yao et al., 2025). According to the World Health Organisation (WHO, 2022), the primary method by which malaria is transmitted to humans is through the bites of female *Anopheles* mosquitoes. The signs and symptoms of malaria may be subtle at first, resembling those of many other feverish conditions. Human malaria is caused by five different species of *Plasmodium* parasites, of which *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* represent the biggest threats. The deadliest malaria parasite, *P. falciparum*, is also the most common in Africa. If *P. falciparum* malaria is not treated, it can cause severe sickness and death in as little as 24 hours.

Although there was a worldwide reduction in the number of malaria cases and the associated death rate during the initial two decades of the twenty-first century, the disease is now back on the rise. It continues to be a major cause of death in low-income countries, especially for children under five in sub-Saharan Africa, following the COVID-19 epidemic and the emergence and dissemination of resistance to widely used anti-malaria (Pell, 2023). Global research highlights that when individuals are empowered and communities are actively involved, they are more likely

to take ownership of health initiatives, maintain long-term commitment, and consistently practice health-promoting behaviours (Kumar & Preetha, 2012). In the end, economic development can be impacted by the direct and indirect costs of illness, disability, and death caused by malaria, and these three outcomes can also have an impact on labour availability and productivity (Ochi et al., 2018).

With over 90% of all malaria-related deaths occurring in tropical regions of sub-Saharan Africa, malaria remains one of the most concerning vector-borne infections in the region despite recent national and international initiatives to combat it, and this is because the disease is almost exclusively a problem in poorly developed tropical or sub-tropical regions (Oladipo et al., 2022). Malaria is a major public health concern in Nigeria, with an estimated 68 million cases and 194,000 deaths due to the disease in 2021 (WHO, 2022). The country has the highest burden of malaria globally, accounting for nearly 27% of the global malaria burden (WHO, 2022). Progress towards further reducing the death toll from malaria has stalled in recent years, and new and complementary approaches are needed to accelerate towards global and national malaria elimination targets (Hetzl et al., 2022). This invariably affects goal three of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which is to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all ages.

This study closes the knowledge gap and offers insight into the rural-urban inequality in Nigeria's usage of mosquito nets. According to Adedokun and Uthman (2020), approximately 53% of the women used mosquito nets; over 60% of these women were poor and illiterate, had tiny households, and resided in the states and areas with the lowest socioeconomic status. This accounts for the rural-urban disparity that occurs in the usage of mosquito nets in Nigeria. The research findings contribute to the understanding of the variables influencing ITN usage in rural and urban regions, which guide future investigations and policy choices. Also, when developing specific measures to boost ITN usage and coverage, the study's findings provide insight into the factors that contribute to disparities in mosquito net usage in Nigeria's rural-urban areas. Rural residents generally have lower levels of formal education and income compared to their urban counterparts, with a study in Nigeria showing that 81% of rural older adults had no formal education versus 50% in urban areas (Cadmus et al., 2021).

Several studies have been conducted on rural-urban inequality in the usage of mosquito nets in a bid to prevent and control malaria. These studies cut across different countries, including Nigeria. For this research, some will be reviewed. The study carried out by Ameyaw (2021) established that in sub-Saharan Africa, ITN utilization varies significantly between communities and geographical areas. Also in Southeast Asia, Report et al. (2016) indicated that “use” as measured by the percentage of household members who slept with an ITN was significantly lower, at 6.9% in urban areas and 15.3% in rural ones in Eastern Myanmar.

On the contrary, the result from the work of Tesfaye et al. (2022) showed that pregnant women who lived in urban areas had twice the probability of using ITNs than those who lived in rural areas in Eastern Ethiopia. Nwachukwu et al. (2022) buttressed this point during the study carried out on Rural-Urban Differentials in Access to Behaviour Change Communication and Use of Long-Lasting Insecticide-Treated Nets and Artemisinin-Based Combination Therapy in Southeast

Nigeria. It was discovered that urban dwellers slept under mosquito nets more frequently than rural ones in the southeastern part of Nigeria. From the above-reviewed literature, most of these studies only focused on "What" without explaining the "why". They confirmed rural-urban inequalities in the usage of ITN without explaining the reasons for the gap between rural and urban usage. This study will fill this major gap in knowledge by using the decomposition method to analyse reasons for the existing inequalities in the usage of ITN in Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

According to a few empirical literature studies, the socio-ecological model serves as the theoretical basis for research on disparities in mosquito net usage. This is because the socio-ecological model explains that community and individual behaviours and features influence the use of insecticide-treated nets, which in turn influences the community's malaria prevalence (Solanke et al., 2023).

Dependent variable

The dependent variable for this study is *Usenet*. It is a measure of whether respondents slept under mosquito nets or not.

Independent variables

In this study, we considered aspects at the household level as well as certain socio-demographic elements based on theory and previous empirical studies. These characteristics were selected because past research had shown a statistically significant correlation between them and the use of mosquito nets.

Specifying the model in a functional form becomes:

$$Usenet = f(age, age2, edulevel, religion, wealth, urban, hhsex, hheadage, hage2, perception, socialmedia, zones) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Usenet: UN is the dependent variable. The observation reveals that 14,476 respondents in Nigeria completed the questionnaire. Our dependent variable is a dummy taking the value of 0-1. This shows that the minimum value is 1. With 1 representing the usage of a mosquito net and 0 representing non-usage.

Zone: It is a variable that represents the geopolitical zones in Nigeria. This includes North-Central, North-East, North-West, South-East, South-South, and South-West.

Urban: This variable is a dummy variable measuring respondents' place of residence, indicating whether it is urban or rural.

Wealth: This is an independent variable that represents the wealth of the household, measured by the quantile of each household.

Religion: This is a static variable. A categorical variable representing religious affiliation. This is simplified into dummy variables. e.g., Catholics, other Christians, Islam, Traditionalists, and Others.

Age: This is also an independent variable. This represents the respondent's age in years. It ranges from 15 to 49 years.

Education: This measures the respondent's years of education. Categorical variable indicating the highest level of education attained by the respondent. This can be broken down into dummy variables. e.g., No education, Primary, Secondary, Tertiary.

Household sex: This is used to measure the gender of the head of the household. It is categorised as male or female.

Age of the Household Head: This is the variable used to measure the age of the household head.

Social media: This is a categorised variable used to measure whether malaria messages were heard/seen via social media. It is measured as 1 for yes and 0 for No.

Perception: This variable represents the respondent's belief on whether they agree or disagree with people who have nets and usually sleep under them every night.

Expressing the model in a linear form,

$$uset_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 age_i + \beta_2 age2_i + \beta_3 edulevel_i + \beta_4 religion_i + \beta_5 wealth_i + \beta_6 urban_i + \beta_7 hhsex_i + \beta_8 hheadage_i + \beta_9 hage2_i + \beta_{10} perception_i + \beta_{11} socialmedia_i + \beta_{12} zones + \mu_i \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where;

β_0 = intercept and

$\beta_1 - \beta_{12}$ = estimated coefficient of the independent variables

This study hinges on the empirical work of Adewara et al (2014) using the Blinder-Oaxaca decomposition method to explain the inequality in the usage of mosquito nets in urban and rural areas. Using the decomposition method, the study demonstrates how disparities in other factors influencing mosquito net usage in urban regions might account for differences in mosquito net usage in rural areas. Thus, if disparities in other variables influencing the use of mosquito nets in urban areas are the cause of inequality in rural areas, then lowering disparities in the variables that influence urban usage of mosquito nets will facilitate the reduction of urban inequality. The primary advantage of breaking down rural-urban inequality into its underlying causes is this.

Therefore, the specification of the study is seen below:

$$y^{rural} - y^{urban} = \beta^{rural} x^{rural} - \beta^{urban} x^{urban} \quad (1)$$

Where x^{rural} and x^{urban} depict vectors of the factors that influence the usage of mosquito nets, such as individual socio-demographic characteristics and factors at the household level that are assessed at the means for rural and urban areas, respectively.

Considering that there are just two explanatory variables, x_1 and x_2 , then,

$$\begin{aligned} y^{rural} - y^{urban} &= (\beta_0^{rural} - \beta_0^{urban}) + (\beta_1^{rural} x_1^{rural} - \beta_1^{urban} x_1^{urban}) + (\beta_2^{rural} x_2^{rural} - \beta_2^{urban} x_2^{urban}) \\ &= G_0 + G_1 + G_2 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The difference in y between the rural and urban areas is said to be caused by (i) differences in the intercepts (G_0), (ii) differences in x_1 and β_1 (G_1) and (iii) differences in x_2 and β_2 (G_2): For example, G_1 may quantify the difference in mean results resulting from variations in mosquito net usage (x_1) and the impacts of using mosquito nets (β_1).

Oaxaca decomposition contributes to the explanation of the particular or overall gap, in the explanatory variable, caused by (i) variations in x 's (the explained component) and (ii) variations in β 's (the unexplained component). The discrepancy in mosquito net usage between rural and urban areas was further explained in two ways:

$$y^{rural} - y^{urban} = \Delta x \beta^{rural} - \Delta x \beta^{urban} \quad (3)$$

Where $\Delta x = x^{rural} - x^{urban}$ and $\Delta \beta = \beta^{rural} - \beta^{urban}$, or

As a result, it is considered that the decomposition in (3) represents a specific instance of a more general decomposition:

$$y^{rural} - y^{urban} = \Delta x \beta^{rural} + \Delta x \beta^{urban} \quad (4)$$

$$y^{rural} - y^{urban} = \Delta x \beta^{rural} + \Delta x \beta^{urban} + \Delta x \Delta \beta \quad (5)$$

$$= E + C + CE$$

The data indicate that the difference in the usage of mosquito nets between the rural and urban areas is caused by differences in endowments (E), coefficients (C), and the interaction of endowments and coefficients (C E).

Data

We analysed the data with STATA version 18. In analysing the data, we followed two stages. In the first stage, two different models were developed, involving multilevel binary logistic regression analyses to assess the effect of socio-demographic and household-level factors on the use of mosquito nets. Model I analysed the effect of only household-level factors, while Model II analysed both socio-demographic and household-level factors on the use of mosquito nets. For the two models, we presented the adjusted odds ratios (AORs) and their associated 95% confidence intervals (CIs). In the second stage, we decompose the urban factor to identify the factors responsible for the disparity in mosquito net usage between rural and urban areas.

Results

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
Respondent use net (Usenet)		
No	8790	60.72
Yes	5686	39.28
Respondents Age Groups		
15-19	2663	18.40
20-24	2466	17.04
25-29	2687	18.56
30-34	2340	16.16
35-39	1998	13.80
40-44	1435	9.91
45-49	887	6.13
Respondents' education (Edulevel)		
No education	4792	33.10
Primary	1977	13.66
Secondary	5669	39.16
Higher	2038	14.08
Respondents Perception		
Disagree/less than half	7302	50.44
Agree/more than half	7174	49.56
Respondents' residence (Urban)		
Rural	9546	65.94
Urban	4930	34.06
Wealth level		
Poorest	2434	16.81
Poorer	2431	16.79
Middle	2802	19.36
Richer	3225	22.28
Richest	3584	24.76
Household head gender (Hhsex)		

Male	12339	85.24
Female	2137	14.76
Geopolitical Zones (zone)		
North central	2674	18.47
North east	2523	17.43
North west	3635	25.11
South east	1523	10.52
South south	2148	14.84
South west	1973	13.63
Respondents' Religion		
Catholic	1301	8.99
Other Christian	5757	39.77
Islam	7344	50.73
Traditionalist	70	0.48
Other	4	0.03
Social media usage (socialmedia)		
No	13687	94.55
Yes	789	5.45
Respondents have net (Net)		
No	5739	39.64
Yes	8737	60.36

Source: Author's Compilation, 2025.

Table 1 above represents the respondents' socio-demographic characteristics. Respondents on Usenet show that 39.28% use mosquito nets, while 60.72% do not. The respondents' age group is 15-49 years, and their educational level ranges from no education to tertiary education. Concerning respondents' perception of the usage of mosquito nets, 50.44% of the respondents disagree, while 49.56% agree. 65.94% of respondents reside in rural areas, while 34.06% reside in urban areas. The wealth quintile ranges from the poorest to the richest. The household head sex represents 85.24% male and 14.76% female. The geopolitical zones range from North Central to South West. Respondents' religions include Catholic, other Christian, Islam, Traditionalist, and other religions. Social media also has 94.55% non-usage and 5.45% usage. 39.64% of respondents do not own a mosquito net, while 60.36% do.

Table 2: Determinants of usage of mosquito nets: ordered logistic regression

VARIABLES	MODEL 1	MODEL2
	Usenet	Usenet
Age	0.058*** (0.014)	0.059*** (0.014)
age2	-0.001*** (0.001)	-0.001*** (0.001)
No education	-0.023 (0.057)	0.035 (0.082)
Primary		0.218***

		(0.082)
Secondary	-0.238*** (0.057)	0.162** (0.067)
Catholic	-0.625*** (0.070)	0.183** (0.082)
Other Christian	-0.404*** (0.046)	0.213*** (0.056)
Traditionalist	-0.796*** (0.292)	-0.575* (0.302)
Others	0.535 (1.012)	1.299 (1.011)
Urban	-0.141*** (0.040)	-0.097** (0.044)
Perception	0.545*** (0.036)	0.403*** (0.038)
Socialmedia	-0.226** (0.091)	-0.083 (0.094)
North east		1.062*** (0.064)
North West		0.969*** (0.061)
South East		-0.842*** (0.084)
South south		-0.665*** (0.074)
South West		-0.418*** (0.072)
Poorest		-0.251*** (0.061)
Middle		0.045 (0.061)
Richer		-0.214*** (0.067)
Richest		-0.284*** (0.078)
Hhsex		-0.106* (0.057)
Hheadage		-0.018*** (0.007)
hage2		4.16e-05 (6.03e-05)
Higher edu	-0.420*** (0.073)	
Zones	-0.152***	

	(0.012)	
Poorer		
Net		
Constant cut1	0.673*** (0.203)	1.105*** (0.299)
Observations	14,476	14,476

Note: Robust Standard errors in parentheses. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1 represent variables significant at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

Source: Author's Compilations, 2025.

Model 1 reveals how certain socio-demographic factors affect the usage of mosquito nets. Age and perception have a positive and significant (at 1% level of significance) relationship with the usage of mosquito nets. This implies that a unit increase in the age of the respondents will increase the odds to a higher degree in the usage of mosquito nets by 0.0584. Also, a unit increase in the belief of people in the usage of mosquito nets will increase the odds of mosquito net usage by 0.545. On the contrary, urban and social media have a negative but significant effect on the usage of mosquito nets at 1% and 5% levels of significance, respectively. This indicates that a unit increase in the urban areas will reduce the odds of mosquito net usage by 0.141. Likewise, a unit increase in people being informed via social media will reduce the odds of using mosquito nets by 0.226. Also, in comparison with those who had only primary education, a unit increase in the number of people with secondary education will reduce the odds of mosquito net usage by 0.238, as there exists a negative but significant (1% level) relationship between those who had a secondary educational degree and the usage of mosquito nets. Also, for those with a higher degree of education, a negative but significant (1% level) association exists between them and the usage of mosquito nets. Therefore, a unit increase in the number of people with higher education will reduce the odds of using mosquito nets by a lower degree by 0.420. Those with no educational background have a negative and insignificant relationship with mosquito net usage compared to those with primary education.

In comparison to those of the Islamic belief, Catholicism has a negative but significant relationship with the usage of mosquito nets. This means that compared to those who practice Islam, a unit increase in those who are Catholics would decrease the odds of the usage of mosquito nets by 0.625. Also, a unit increase in other Christians who are not Catholics in comparison with those who practice Islam will reduce the odds of mosquito net usage by 0.404, as there exists a negative but significant relationship between other Christians and the usage of mosquito nets, which will reduce the odds of mosquito net usage by 0.152.

Model 2 results show a combination of household factors and socio-demographic factors, along with their effect on the usage of mosquito nets. Similar to the results in Model 2, age and perception have a positive and significant ($p < 0.01$) effect on the use of mosquito nets. This implies that the odds of mosquito net usage will increase by 0.0587 for every unit increase in the age of the

respondents. The same applies to people's beliefs and perceptions about the use of mosquito nets. An increase in their perception will also increase the odds of mosquito net usage by 0.403. Age² as in Model 1, has a negative but significant ($p < 0.01$) association with the use of mosquito nets. Regarding individuals with higher education, the relationship between those with only a primary school education and the use of mosquito nets is positive and significant ($p < 0.01$). This indicates that the odds of using mosquito nets will increase by 0.218 if there is a unit increase in those with only a primary education, compared to those with higher education. Likewise, a unit increase in those with a secondary school education compared to those with higher education will increase the odds of using mosquito nets by 0.162. This is because of the positive and significant ($p < 0.05$) relationship that exists between individuals with a secondary school education and the use of mosquito nets. Additionally, individuals with no educational background have a positive but insignificant relationship with those who use mosquito nets compared to those with higher education.

Urban has a negative but significant (5% level) association with mosquito net usage. This implies that a unit increase in the number of people in urban areas will reduce the odds of mosquito net usage by 0.0968. In comparison with those who practice Islam, those who are Catholics have a positive and significant relationship with the usage of mosquito nets. This means that a unit increase in Catholics will also increase the odds of mosquito net usage. Furthermore, other Christians, in comparison to those who practice Islam, have a positive and significant association with mosquito net usage. This means that a unit increase in those who are Christians in comparison to Muslims will increase the odds of mosquito net usage by 0.213.

Table 3: Blinder-Oaxaca Group Differences in Rural–Urban utilisation of mosquito nets in Nigeria

Inequality in the usage of mosquito nets	Within Rural	Within Urban	Rural-urban gap
Blinder-Oaxaca	0.419*** (0.005)	0.341*** (0.007)	0.078*** (0.008)

*Source: The author's computation. The indicators of statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels are ***, **, and *.*

The rural-urban inequality in the usage of mosquito nets in Nigeria is presented in Table 3 above. The results indicate that in the rural area, the coefficient of the usage of mosquito net, which is significant at a 1% level, is 0.419, as shown in column 1. Likewise, in column 2, in the urban area, the usage of mosquito nets has a coefficient of 0.341 at 1% level of significance. The difference between mosquito net usage in the rural area and in the urban area, shown in column 3, is 0.078, and it is significant at 1% level. This implies that there exists a significant inequality in the usage of mosquito nets in the rural-urban areas.

Table 4: Decomposition of rural-urban inequality in the usage of mosquito nets in Nigeria

VARIABLES	Endowments	Coefficients	Interaction
Age	-0.006 (0.005)	0.169 (0.183)	-0.005 (0.006)
age2	0.005	-0.069	0.005

	(0.005)	(0.098)	(0.006)
Edulevel	0.013**	0.047**	-0.017**
	(0.006)	(0.019)	(0.007)
Perception	0.004***	0.021***	0.002**
	(0.001)	(0.008)	(0.001)
Socialmedia	0.001	-0.003	0.002
	(0.001)	(0.003)	(0.002)
South	0.024***	-0.045***	0.013***
	(0.003)	(0.009)	(0.003)
Wealth	0.023**	0.006	-0.002
	(0.009)	(0.036)	(0.011)
Hhsex	0.003***	0.047*	-0.002*
	(0.001)	(0.027)	(0.001)
Hheadage	-0.002	-0.458***	0.003
	(0.001)	(0.131)	(0.003)
hage2	0.001	0.195***	-0.001
	(0.002)	(0.059)	(0.002)
Total	0.065***	0.016*	-0.003
	(0.007)	(0.009)	(0.008)
Constant		0.106	
		(0.132)	
Observations	14,476	14,476	14,476

*Source: The computation of the author.2025. Indicators of statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels are ***, **, and *.*

In Table 4, the study breaks down the findings in Table 3 into the factors that contribute to the disparity in the utilisation of mosquito nets in both urban and rural areas. The result revealed that at a 1% level of significance, edulevel positively affects rural-urban disparity in the usage of mosquito nets. This implies that the educational gap in the rural-urban areas contributes positively to the inequality in the usage of mosquito nets that exist in the rural-urban areas in Nigeria. Perception gap on the usage of mosquito nets that exist in the rural-urban areas also contributes positively and significantly to the rural-urban differences that exist in the usage of mosquito nets. Likewise, another significant factor that causes the rural-urban inequality in the usage of mosquito nets is the north-south dichotomy. It positively impacts the differences in mosquito net usage. Moreover, the sex of the household head and the disparity in wealth quintiles between rural and urban areas positively influence the rural-urban difference in the utilisation of mosquito nets. On the other hand, a reduction in the age of the household head will, at a 1% level of significance, lower the inequality that exists in the usage of mosquito nets in the urban and rural areas.

The findings reveal that the educational divide, wealth quintile disparity, and perceptual differences between rural and urban areas contribute to heightened rural-urban inequality in mosquito net utilisation, and these disparities should be mitigated.

Discussion

The results show that there exists an inequality in the usage of mosquito nets between rural and urban areas. Additionally, a disparity in the utilisation of mosquito nets occurs between rural and urban areas. This means that there is variation in the number of people who sleep under the nets in rural areas compared to those in urban areas. The findings in Table 3 revealed that the utilisation of mosquito nets is more prominent in urban areas than in rural areas. This might be because urban areas often have better access to healthcare infrastructure, which can facilitate the distribution and teaching of ITNs. Effective public health campaigns can lead to increased knowledge and usage of ITNs, maximising their economic benefits. This finding aligns with the results of Nwachukwu et al. (2022). The findings, which support the work of Kuetche et al. (2023) and Budu et al. (2022), further revealed that educational level has an impact on the disparity in the use of mosquito nets in rural and urban areas in Nigeria. This is because higher education makes it possible for a person to have better access to resources and health knowledge, which helps them to take preventative action, such as the utilisation of mosquito nets. This is more common in urban populations than in their rural counterparts, which exacerbates the disparity.

Additionally, the results indicate that the respondents' belief in the use of mosquito nets influences the rural-urban disparity. The result showed that an increase in perception would increase the inequality gap. Given their greater access to resources and information, urban inhabitants may be more inclined to act on growing convictions about the effectiveness of mosquito nets. However, despite equal levels of belief in their efficacy, rural communities may continue to be poorly informed or lack access to high-quality nets, resulting in a discrepancy in actual usage. The study carried out by Duodu et al. (2021) also reiterated that rural Nigerian women who view malaria as a serious threat are less likely to use treated bed nets. Wealth is also seen to positively affect the rural-urban disparity in the use of mosquito nets. Wealthier urban households usually have easier access to financing, making it easier for them to buy mosquito nets. Their ability to purchase higher-quality nets, such as long-lasting insecticide-treated nets (LLINs), which are more successful in stopping the spread of malaria, is made possible by their financial flexibility. This spurs usage in comparison to the rural areas, causing a rise in the rural-urban disparity in mosquito net usage. This supports the findings of Seyoum et al. (2023) and Haileselassie et al. (2023).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined socio-demographic and household disparities influencing the use of mosquito nets across Nigeria. The findings clearly demonstrate that mosquito net usage is not uniform across rural and urban areas. The study also finds that religious affiliation and urban residency are important determinants of mosquito net usage. Urban residents are less likely to use nets, possibly because they perceive a reduced malaria risk, have better housing, or are less exposed to targeted distribution efforts. In conclusion, malaria prevention efforts in Nigeria must move beyond uniform national policies toward more context-sensitive approaches. Addressing disparities in mosquito net usage requires a deep understanding of socio-economic, educational, and cultural factors. This study therefore recommended that the government implement residence-specific education and communication strategies to address socio-economic, gender, and perceptual disparities, while promoting equitable distribution and targeted behaviour change across rural and

urban populations. Also, this study emphasises the importance of establishing achievable targets to alleviate disparities in education, socioeconomic status, and perceptions between rural and urban areas.

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